

Abdumalikova Zebiniso
Masters student
Tashkent State University of
Uzbek language and literature
named after Alisher Navoi

Abdumalikova Zebiniso
Magistratura talabasi
Alisher Navoiy nomidagi
Toshkent davlat o'zbek tili
va adabiyoti universiteti

Абдумаликова Зебинисо
студент магистратуры
Ташкентский
государственный
университет узбекского
языка и литературы имени
Алишера Навои

EXPLORING THE MULTIFACETED DIMENSIONS OF LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS

ABSTRACT: This article delves into the intricate facets of linguistic personality within the realm of contemporary linguistics. It navigates through the attempts to comprehend the concept of "linguistic personality," examining its structure, and classifying its models. Rooted in the paradigm of anthropocentrism, the study underscores the indispensability of language in understanding the human experience. Linguoculturology emerges as a promising field, with "linguistic personality" at its core. The article explores various linguistic personality models, considering linguistic, linguoculturological, and communicative aspects. It discusses the interplay of language, culture, and ethnicity, presenting a synthesis of linguistic personalities across diverse individuals within a language.

KEY WORDS: linguistic personality, linguoculturology, anthropocentrism, communicative approach, language proficiency, cultural synthesis, linguistic models, individuality, intertextuality, hierarchical structure.

In modern linguistics, there are widespread attempts to comprehend the concept of "linguistic personality," define its structure, and classify its models. This is due to the fact that anthropocentrism is currently a fundamental characteristic of the paradigm of scientific humanitarian knowledge, and understanding a person is impossible without studying language. Linguoculturology is one of the new and

promising directions in linguistics, where the defining concept is "linguistic personality."

The term "linguistic personality" was introduced into scientific discourse by B.V. Vinogradov in the 1930s in the book "On the Language of Fictional Prose." He explored two aspects of the artistic linguistic personality – the author's

personality and the character's personality [Vinogradov V.V., 1930, 91 p.].

In linguistics, "linguistic personality" refers to a speech personality – a person as a language user, observed in terms of their ability for speech activity, i.e., a complex of psycho-physiological properties enabling them to produce and perceive speech works [Bogin V.I., 1984, 3 p.]. In Russian linguistics, the most well-known concept of linguistic personality is that of Yu.N. Karaulov. According to him, linguistic personality appears as *homo loquens* in general, and the ability to use language is considered a generic characteristic of humans (*homo sapiens*). In this concept, "linguistic personality" encompasses "a set of abilities and characteristics of a person, determining the creation and perception of their speech works (texts), which differ in the degree of structural-linguistic complexity, depth, and accuracy of reflecting reality, and goal orientation" [Karaulov Yu.N., 2002].

Different approaches exist for studying linguistic personality, covering a multitude of interpretations. Considering the goals of our research, we will explore the following approaches: linguoculturological, linguodidactic, and communicative. These proposed directions are distinguishable by their methods of describing linguistic personality and the scope of the issues they cover.

Linguoculturology emphasizes a collective cultural-historical image; the personality existing in the cultural space

and reflected in language; and the national-cultural prototype of the language user. The focus of research becomes the synthetic image of linguistic personality formed by various individuals in the language. Linguoculturology directs attention to the interconnection of "language – culture – ethnicity," aiming to study the material and spiritual culture embodied in a living national language and manifested in language processes [M.B. Emich, 1994].

The linguoculturological approach, based on the structural organization of linguistic personality proposed by Yu.N. Karaulov, led to the identification of various variations of linguistic personality: multi-human and partial-human personalities (V.P. Neroznak), ethno-semantic personality (S.G. Vorkachev), Russian linguistic personality (Yu.N. Karaulov), linguistic and speech personalities (Yu.E. Prokhorov, L.P. Klobukova), emotional linguistic personality (V.I. Shakhovskiy).

Thus, in the linguocultural aspect, language, culture, and ethnicity are inseparably linked and form the focus of the personality – the junction of its physical, spiritual, and social self. The communicative approach to linguistic personality has gained the most recognition. Here, linguistic personality is defined as a "communicative-activity unit, representing a two-member 'speaker and listener'" [Vinokur G.O., 1990, 518 p.].

The concept of communicative personality is of interest, highlighting

cognitive, behavioral, and holistic aspects of this notion [Karasik V.I., 1986, 3-16 p.]. One of the most important directions in the study of linguistic personality is the examination of linguistic personality in artistic texts. In artistic texts, linguistic personality can be perceived as "a certain (linguistic) correlate of the spiritual image of a complete personality" [Karasik V.I., 2004, 71 p.]. The character, as a linguistic personality, embodies cultural, communicative-activity values, knowledge, attitudes, and behavioral reactions.

One of the crucial components of the theory of linguistic personality is its structure, extensively described in the works of Yu.N. Karaulov on the Russian language. According to his work, the structure of linguistic personality consists of three levels: 1) verbal-semantic, realized in the description of formal means expressing specific meanings (i.e., the description of the lexical, grammatical, etc., structure of language); 2) cognitive, where units are concepts, ideas, concepts formed by each linguistic individual into a "worldview" reflecting the hierarchy of the individual's values (frame, phraseological units, aphorisms, metaphors, etc.); 3) pragmatic, studying goals, motives, interests, methods of argumentation, evaluation, etc. In the analysis of linguistic personality, this level ensures the logical transition from assessing their speech activity to understanding real-world activities [Karaulov Yu.N., 1987: 87]. Other researchers also identify three levels of linguistic personality. For example, I.P. Susov distinguishes the formal-semantic,

cognitive-interpretative, and socio-interactive [Susov I.P., 1988, 7-13 p.].

One of the key components of the theory of linguistic personality is its structure, detailed by Y.N. Kuraulov in the context of the Russian language. According to his work, the linguistic personality structure consists of three levels: 1) verbal-semantic, involving the description of formal means expressing specific meanings (e.g., lexical and grammatical structures); 2) cognitive, where units include concepts, ideas, and concepts forming an individual's "worldview" reflecting the hierarchy of personal values; 3) pragmatic, studying goals, motives, interests, argumentation methods, evaluations, etc.

V.D. Lyutikova holds a different perspective: "The hierarchical model of linguistic personality, developed by researchers, reflects a generalized personality type, making it not always applicable for the study of an individual personality. In an individual speech situation, verbal, cognitive, and pragmatic levels are identifiable. Additionally, any personality combines elements of stability and variability, is subject to external influences, and is not devoid of internal conflicts. The presence of stability and variability in the linguistic personality, influenced by various factors, further complicates the structure of the linguistic personality" [Lyutikova V.D., 1999, p. 9]. Suhykh, in his works, examines the substantial and intentional levels of linguistic personality [Suhykh S.A., 1993]. The levels of correctness, interiorization,

saturation, adequate choice, and synthesis are proposed by Susov [Susov I.P., 1988, pp. 7-13]. The levels offered by G.I. Bogin are also considered [Bogin G.I., 1975, p. 3]. N.A. Kuzmina highlights the intertextual component in the structure of linguistic personality, involving knowledge of a certain number of texts from a given culture and their symbolic representatives – quotations. The degree of influence of literary texts on linguistic personality and the nature of the precedent intertextual part of the individual thesaurus are established [Kuzmina N.A., 2006, p. 272].

The linguistic personality in an artistic text is determined by a category that has an internal structure and external signs of realization. On this basis, a model of linguistic personality in an artistic dialogue was developed by Normurodova N.Z. It consists of the following levels: -semantic-stylistic; -linguopragmatic; -linguocognitive; -linguoculturological [Normurodova N.Z., 2012]. This model of linguistic personality is based on Yu.N. Karaulov's model but includes some changes, additions, and clarifications. It differs in the number of identified levels and incorporates the linguoculturological level. Additionally, in the proposed model, each level is verbal, necessitated by the need for a detailed analysis of linguistic means at each level.

It should be noted that the delineation of levels in the structure of linguistic personality is highly conditional. In real life, there is mutual penetration and interdependence of all levels. Linguistic personality is both the level of language

proficiency and the degree of influence of individuals on the development of language, especially literary language. Communication is not just a conversation between two individuals; it is their mastery of the culture of a particular people or society, as culture (spiritual culture) reveals the measure of human and social in a person. This property of linguistic personality is manifested in language knowledge, in the ability to use them, and in style, and finally, in specific sentences [Stepanova Yu.V., 2012, No. 1].

The artistic text is also a source for studying linguistic personality, both of the author and the characters of the work, considering that characters are a creation of the author's thought. The author manifests themselves differently in the text, but always through words. Giving life to their characters on the pages of the work, the author imparts to them a fragment of their linguistic personality.

In conclusion, it is necessary to emphasize that the study of linguistic personality requires a comprehensive approach to its analysis, taking into account linguistic, linguoculturological, and communicative features of linguistic personality and a detailed examination of the structure of linguistic personality.

The distinction of levels in the linguistic personality structure is somewhat conditional. In real life, there is mutual permeation and interdependence of all levels. Linguistic personality involves language proficiency, the influence of individuals on language development, and

the complex interplay of linguistic, cultural, and communicative aspects. Furthermore, the study of linguistic personality in literary texts reveals insights into both the author and the characters, as characters are born from the author's thought. The author's linguistic personality manifests uniquely in the text through behavior, thought, and language nuances. In conclusion, a comprehensive approach to linguistic personality analysis, considering linguistic, linguo-cultural, and communicative features, is essential.

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